

SEEING 6-D

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BASIS

ABSTRACT

The planes of reference are important to understand the anatomical positioning of various body structures. This educative editorial helps in understanding the various planes of reference to understand key anatomical landmarks.

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Planes of Reference are important to study the relationship of one structure to the other or to accurately explain its position.

Sagittal plane/Longitudinal plane: An anatomical plane which divides the body into RIGHT & LEFT parts.

Hint to memorize: Passing through **sagittal suture** and dividing the whole body into **long** parts – Right and Left.

Frontal/Coronal plane: An anatomical plane which divides the body into: ANTERIOR & POSTERIOR portions.

Hint to memorize: Divides the planes into **front** (anterior) and back (posterior) parts across the direction of **coronal suture**.

Transverse plane/Cross sectional: An anatomical plane which divides the body into SUPERIOR & INFERIOR portions.

Hint to memorize: It **crosses** the whole body and **transverses** it into upper and lower part.

Matter of fact: The planes of reference are based on the Leonardo Da Vinci's 'Anatomical Man' with the only difference being that the arms are down on the side.

